

Supplementary Information to Ezhova et al. ‘Organic aerosol enhances boreal forest photosynthesis under cumulus clouds’

Supplementary Figure 1. Solar zenith angle (SZA) as a function of cloud fraction (a); diurnal cycle of cloud fraction (b). Blue notched boxes show median values and interquartile ranges (IQR, 25 to 75 percentile) of SZA and cloud fraction under low OA loading, and red notched boxes - under high OA loading. Whiskers denote 1.5 IQR range, and the remaining points are ‘outliers’. Black crosses show mean values.

Supplementary Figure 2. Illustration of sampling for low and high aerosol loading and the curve for GPP correction. Red and blue vertical bars show the distribution of low and high aerosol samples over July and August, while transparent horizontal bars under the x -axis mark July and August. Black points are median GPP values for a given day, over years 2012-2018. Black line is a hyperbolic tangent best fit to the GPP. The line clearly shows a mid-August decrease related to seasonal changes.

Supplementary Figure 3. (a) Correlation between AOD and OA mass. (b) Contours of clear sky diffuse radiation as a function of solar zenith angle and aerosol optical depth modelled using SOLIS. Arrow corresponds to an increase in diffuse radiation when aerosol loading increases from low to high and when solar zenith angle decreases from 55° (median value under low aerosol conditions and lowest CF) to 47° (median value under high aerosol conditions and lowest CF).

Supplementary Figure 4. Solar zenith angle (a) and radiation at the top of atmosphere (b) as a function of time of the day. Blue notched boxes show median values and interquartile ranges (IQR, 25 to 75 percentile) of SZA and radiation at the top of atmosphere under low OA loading, and red notched boxes - under high OA loading. Whiskers denote 1.5 IQR range, and the remaining points are 'outliers'. Black crosses show mean values.

Supplementary Figure 5. Diffuse fraction as a function of cloud fraction (a) and time of the day (b). Blue notched boxes show median values and interquartile ranges (IQR, 25 to 75 percentile) of diffuse fraction under low OA loading, and red notched boxes - under high OA loading. Whiskers denote 1.5 IQR range, and the remaining points are ‘outliers’. Black crosses show mean values.. Median diffuse fraction reaches optimal conditions for photosynthesis at CF 0.4-0.8 under low aerosol load and CF 0.2-0.6 at high aerosol load. Median diffuse fraction for cumulus clouds is near optimal for photosynthesis at 0.4-0.5 all day long. In the morning and evening hours, when the difference in diffuse radiation is largest, the diffuse radiation values in the interquartile range fully cover the optimal interval for high aerosol loading, whereas they are somewhat suboptimal at diffuse fractions corresponding to low aerosol loading.

Supplementary Figure 6. Global radiation (a) as a function of cloud fraction; (b) as a function of hour (diurnal cycle). Blue notched boxes show median values and interquartile ranges (IQR, 25 to 75 percentile) of radiation under low OA loading, and red notched boxes - under high OA loading. Whiskers denote 1.5 IQR range, and the remaining points are ‘outliers’. Black crosses show mean values. There is a statistically significant difference in global radiation at two lowest CF (a). In panel (b), even though median global radiation values are somewhat larger under high aerosol loading, the difference is not statistically significant.

Supplementary Figure 7. Air temperature (a) as a function of cloud fraction; (b) as a function of hour (diurnal cycle). Blue notched boxes show median values and interquartile ranges (IQR, 25 to 75 percentile) of air temperature under low OA loading, and red notched boxes - under high OA loading. Whiskers denote 1.5 IQR range, and the remaining points are ‘outliers’. Black crosses show mean values. There is a statistically significant difference in air temperature for all CF and hours.

Supplementary Figure 8. Vapour pressure deficit (a) as a function of cloud fraction; (b) as a function of hour (diurnal cycle). Blue notched boxes show median values and interquartile ranges (IQR, 25 to 75 percentile) of VPD under low OA loading, and red notched boxes - under high OA loading. Whiskers denote 1.5 IQR range, and the remaining points are ‘outliers’. Black crosses show mean values. There is statistically significant difference in VPD at CF between 0.0 and 0.8 (marginal at 0.6-0.8). In panel (b), the difference between VPD values under low and high aerosol loading is statistically significant from 10:00 to 14:00 LT.

Supplementary Figure 9. GPP increase with diffuse radiation. Boxes show median values and interquartile ranges (IQR, 25 to 75 percentile) of GPP for different diffuse radiation bins. Vertical lines denote 1.5 IQR range, and the remaining points are ‘outliers’. Blue and red arrows point at an increase in GPP when CF changes from 0.2-0.4 to 0.4-0.6 under low and high aerosol loading respectively.